

Directly Cooled Silicon Carbide Power Modules: Thermal Model and Experimental Characterization

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Abstract

The Silicon Carbide (SiC) semiconductor material is playing a fundamental role in the development of new power modules. Due to its excellent physical properties, the power devices based on this novel compound improve the traction inverter performance in electric vehicles. This work presents a 3D Finite Element Model (FEM) and fluid dynamics simulation to investigate the behavior of a directly cooled SiC module structure. Furthermore, a two-step experimental procedure to thermally characterize the module is also reported. It comprises a calibration and, subsequently, the thermal impedance computation. The proposed FEM model is compared with experimental test results in order to demonstrate its effectiveness.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, one of the most important research fields is focused on the electric vehicles sector, both for industries and academia [1],[2]. These vehicle types include new semiconductor components and systems which are based on power electronics not present in traditional fueled systems. Wide band gap semiconductors (WBG), such as Silicon Carbide (SiC) [1], [3]-[4] and Gallium Nitride (GaN) [5],[6], are a new enabler technology in order to boost the efficiency of high-power converters in the framework of automotive applications because of their superior features in comparison with silicon. Moreover, this technology allows higher power density and integration that, at the same time, should be carefully addressed with appropriate thermal management systems.

The very impressive properties of WBG also result in lower switching and conduction power losses: this allows for greater system efficiency when SiC or GaN power devices are employed. Lower losses at turn-on and turn-off are due to the possibility to operate at higher frequency in WBG devices based converters. However, issues related to overvoltages and glitches due to high dv/dt and di/dt must be carefully addressed [7]. SiC-based discrete and module [8] devices are increasingly involved not only in the main inverter feeding the

motor, but also in on-board battery chargers and DC-DC architectures [1]. Usually, it is of paramount importance to model heat in the power module, including the heatsink, for establishing the dies thermal behavior [9]. This is mandatory for reliability assessment [10],[11]. In the reliability framework, power cycling tests are employed to experimentally test SiC based power devices and modules [12]. These types of tests follow the specifications provided by the AQG324 normative [13]. The target of power cycles is to enhance the failure mechanisms related to the fatigue of package interconnections, such as wire bonding and substrate attach [14],[15].

Thermal behavior and, consequently, reliability strongly depend on the die attach technique, too. In fact, both soldered and silver sintered solutions can be implemented. However, the latter is preferable to optimize thermal performances and reliability [16]. Due to higher thermal conductivity, sintering slightly enhances power dissipation while realizing a more reliable joint, both for passive and active thermal stress, between die and substrate. Considering the high current which flows in the module, it is expected that they would encounter various thermal reliability issues originating from their high power density, hence the cooling system plays a key role in reliability. Direct liquid cooling,

with pin-fin at the module baseplate, is implemented as a method for allowing an efficient heat exchange [17]. In general, simulation studies are being more and more important in power module development [18]. In this paper, a SiC liquid cooled power module is studied from both experimental and simulation points of view. Furthermore, cross-heating among dies connected in parallel in these structures must be carefully addressed [19]. A Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is carried out with the aim of simulating the module thermal behavior. The proposed model considers the mutual interactions between the dies, as previously mentioned. Various environmental conditions are simulated accounting for the heat flux in multiple layers comprising cooler, package, and the baseplate.

The final aim of this work is to evaluate, both experimentally and numerically, the transient thermal impedance of a directly cooled SiC power module. The paper is organized as follows: in section 2, firstly the SiC power module is briefly described, then the experimental setup and results are reported. In section 3, the simulation activity is outlined, including thermal and fluid dynamics aspects. Finally, in section 4 a comparison between the two frameworks is given, and in section 5 the conclusions are drawn.

2 Module description and experimental results

2.1 Module description

The simulation and the experimental trials described in the present paper have been performed on ST ACEPACK DRIVE®, a power module that contains SiC devices arranged in a three-phase inverter topology. More specifically,

Figure 1 Cooler structure examined in the paper

each switch is made up by eight dies in parallel. The power module's thermal dissipation system is simulated considering both the conduction and the convection heat transfer modes, reproducing the real cooling system behavior, as depicted in Fig. 1. Directly liquid cooling, with pin-fins at the module baseplate, is implemented for an efficient heat exchange in terms of cooling performances and dimension.

2.2 Experimental results

In this sub-section, experimental results obtained will be showed. The aim is to compute thermal impedance of the power module described above. Now, a brief description of the used method is reported. Regarding the experimental test, the virtual junction temperature can be calculated by using the body diode drop voltage during the off-state period, when a negative V_{GS} voltage is applied to the MOSFET. Then, it is possible to compute the thermal impedance Z_{th} . Temperature-sensitive electrical parameter is a technique used in this type of characterization, which relies on different electric semiconductor device parameters that depend on temperature [14], [16], [20]. The formula is reported here below:

$$Z_{th}(t) = \frac{(T_j(t_0) - T_{fluid}(t_0)) - (T_j(t) - T_{fluid}(t))}{V_{DS,max} \cdot I_{LOAD}} \quad (1)$$

where t_0 is time, equal to 100 μs in this framework, at which the first measure is executed, T_j and T_{fluid} are, respectively, the virtual junction temperature and the fluid temperature, while $V_{DS,max}$ is the maximum MOSFET forward voltage and I_{LOAD} is the current. The calibration of body diode drop voltage has been done heating the coolant by external temperature unit. Thermal equilibrium between fluid and power modules is reached when the power module embedded-NTC temperature and the body diode drop voltage are constant with respect to the time. This procedure is repeated for

Figure 2 Drop diode voltage vs temperature calibration curve

Figure 3 Fluid velocity inside the cooler

Figure 4 Thermal map

each calibration temperature. Fig. 2 shows a typical calibration curve in which body drop voltage (V_{SD}) has been plotted with temperature that ranges between RT and 100 °C.

3 Simulations

In this section, the simulation setup and conditions data are given, showing also some pictures on thermal and fluid dynamic results. The power module's thermal dissipation system is simulated considering both the conduction and the convection heat transfer modes, reproducing the real cooling system, as depicted in Fig. 1. A solution made up by water and glycol (in the ratio of 50/50 %) flows in the cooler from the inlet to the outlet manifolds, fixing a flow rate of 6 l/min which implies a laminar flow inside of the cooling system. The air temperature around the modules is maintained fixed at a typical ambient value, while the fluid inlet temperature is established at 50°C. The outlet fluid temperature is a simulation output. This fixed set-up has allowed to simulate the temperature distribution. Fig. 3 depicts the fluid dynamics simulation output in terms of fluid

Figure 5 Simulated thermal impedance semi-logarithmic graph

velocity. Fig. 4 shows the simulated thermal map, as obtained powering on two switches. It can be observed that the simulated temperatures are quite similar in the considered dies. By applying the well-known formula previously explained, the $Z_{thj-fluid}$ can be computed having the information about the average switch junction temperature, the fluid temperature, and the power applied to the DUTs.

Moreover, in order to consider the cross coupling heat flow occurring among the dice, the mutual thermal impedance between one die, which is dissipating the power losses, and its neighbor one, with both that are just sensing the temperature dissipated by the single die, has also been evaluated [21]-[23]. In Fig. 5, the normalized thermal impedance is shown. The blue curve represents the thermal behavior of the die where the power losses is provided, while the other three curves are referred to the neighbor devices. The observed delay between the curves is due to the heat propagation in the material, the geometry, and the distance from the source and the other dies.

Figure 6 Measured and simulated thermal impedance semi-logarithmic graph

4 Comparison between experimental and simulation results

Experimental tests with the same conditions are performed in order to calibrate the developed model. In this section, a comparison between experimental and simulation results, which are presented previously in the paper, is executed. The graph depicted in Fig. 6 shows a good correspondence between the experimental and the FEA thermal impedance results, thus confirming the goodness of the model. More in detail, it is possible to note that there is a little misalignment, between the two curves, in the central zone of the graph (0.01s-0.01s). In particular, there is a slightly delay of the measured curve, probably due to different capacitance values in the two cases.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, a directly cooled power module, made up of silicon carbide, has been studied both experimentally and numerically. The experiment method, using body diode drop voltage measurement during the off-state period, has been considered. Then, thermal simulations, considering also module's fluid dynamics, have been carried out. It has been seen how the simulation results fit quite well with the experimental ones, as it has been pointed out in the paper. More specifically, the testing phase has coped with the thermal impedance evaluation. Then, a finite element and fluid dynamics simulation has been considered to compute the same quantities obtained in the experimental phase.

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7 References:

- [1] G. Mauromicale, A. Raciti, S. A. Rizzo, G. Susinni, L. Abbatelli, S. Buonomo, D. Cavallaro, V. Giuffrida, "SiC Power Modules for Traction Inverters in Automotive Applications," *IECON 2019*, pp. 1973-1978.
- [2] A. K. Morya et al., "Wide Bandgap Devices in AC Electric Drives: Opportunities and Challenges," in *IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 3-20, March 2019.
- [3] X. She, A. Q. Huang, Ó. Lucía and B. Ozpineci, "Review of Silicon Carbide Power Devices and Their Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 8193-8205, Oct. 2017.
- [4] A.A. Messina, A. Imbruglia, M. Calabretta, V. Vinciguerra, C.C. Moise, A. Sitta, A., M. Enachescu, F. Roccaforte, "The "first and euRoPEAn siC eight Inches piOt liNe": a project, called REACTION, that will boost key SiC Technologies upgrading (developments) in Europe, unleashing Applications in the Automotive Power Electronics Sector," *2020 AEIT International Conference of Electrical and Electronic Technologies for Automotive (AEIT AUTOMOTIVE)*, Turin, Italy, 2020, pp. 1-6.
- [5] F. Roccaforte, P. Fiorenza, G. Greco, R. Lo Nigro, F. Giannazzo, F. Iucolano, et al., "Emerging trends in wide band gap semiconductors (SiC and GaN) technology for power devices", in *Microelectronic Engineering*, pp. 187-188, 2018.
- [6] E.A. Jones, F. F. Wang and D. Costinett, "Review of Commercial GaN Power Devices and GaN-Based Converter Design Challenges," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 707-719, Sept. 2016.
- [7] G. Mauromicale, A. Raciti, S.A. Rizzo, G. Susinni, L. Abbatelli, S. Buonomo, V. Giuffrida, A. Raffa, "Improvement of SiC power module layout to mitigate the gate-source overvoltage during switching operation," *2019 AEIT International Conference of Electrical and Electronic Technologies for Automotive (AEIT AUTOMOTIVE)*, Torino, Italy, 2019, pp. 1-6.
- [8] H. Lee, V. Smet and R. Tummala, "A Review of SiC Power Module Packaging Technologies: Challenges, Advances, and Emerging Issues," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power*

- Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 239-255, March 2020.
- [9] G. Bazzano, D. Cavallaro, A. Raffa, F. Di Giovanni, A. Manzitto and A. Cascio, "Modeling Techniques and Virtual Prototyping of Silicon Carbide MOSFET and IGBT Power Modules," *IESES 2020*, Cagliari, Italy, 2020, pp. 371-376.
- [10] A. Manzitto, V. Giuffrida, D. Cavallaro and G. Bazzano, "Finite Element Method Integration on Mission Profile for Silicon Carbide (SiC) MOSFET Power Module used in the EV Traction Inverter," *PCIM Europe digital days 2020*, Germany, 2020, pp. 1-6.
- [11] M. Calabretta, M. Renna, V. Vinciguerra and A. A. Messina, "Power Packages Interconnections for High Reliability Automotive Applications," *ESSDERC 2019 - 49th European Solid-State Device Research Conference (ESSDERC)*, Cracow, Poland, 2019, pp. 35-39.
- [12] C. Durand, M. Klingler, D. Coutellier and H. Naceur, "Power Cycling Reliability of Power Module: A Survey," in *IEEE Transactions on Device and Materials Reliability*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 80-97, March 2016.
- [13] "ECPE Guideline AQG 324 Qualification of Power Modules for Use in Power Electronics Converter Units in Motor Vehicles." (2019).
- [14] G. Zeng, H. Cao, W. Chen and J. Lutz, "Difference in Device Temperature Determination Using p-n-Junction Forward Voltage and Gate Threshold Voltage," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 2781-2793, March 2019.
- [15] Z. Ni, X. Lyu, O. P. Yadav, B. N. Singh, S. Zheng and D. Cao, "Overview of Real-Time Lifetime Prediction and Extension for SiC Power Converters," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 8, pp. 7765-7794, Aug. 2020.
- [16] A. Sitta, M. Renna, A. A. Messina, G. Sequenzia, G. D'Arrigo and M. Calabretta., "Thermal measurement and numerical analysis for automotive power modules," *EuroSimE 2020*, Cracow, Poland, 2020, pp. 1-3.
- [17] M. Baumann, J. Lutz and W. Wondrak, "Liquid cooling methods for power electronics in an automotive environment," *Proceedings of the 2011 14th European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications*, Birmingham, 2011, pp. 1-8.
- [18] A. B. Jørgensen, S. Munk-Nielsen and C. Uhrenfeldt, "Overview of Digital Design and Finite-Element Analysis in Modern Power Electronic Packaging," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 35, no. 10, pp. 10892-10905, Oct. 2020.
- [19] A. S. Bahman, K. Ma, P. Ghimire, F. Iannuzzo and F. Blaabjerg, "A 3-D-Lumped Thermal Network Model for Long-Term Load Profiles Analysis in High-Power IGBT Modules," in *IEEE Trans. Emerg. Sel. Topics Power Electron.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 1050-1063, Sept. 2016.
- [20] J. Lutz, "Power cycling – methods, measurement accuracy, comparability," *CIPS 2020*, Berlin, Germany, 2020, pp. 1-8
- [21] Martin Marz, Paul Nance, Infineon Technologies AG Munich, "Thermal Modeling of Power-electronic Systems".
- [22] J. Li, A. Castellazzi, M. A. Eleffendi, E. Gurpinar, C. M. Johnson and L. Mills, "A Physical RC Network Model for Electrothermal Analysis of a Multichip SiC Power Module," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 33, no. 3.
- [23] H. Li, X. Liao, Z. Zeng, Y. Hu, Y. Li, S. Liu, L. Ran, "Thermal Coupling Analysis in a Multichip Paralleled IGBT Module for a DFIG Wind Turbine Power Converter," in *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion* vol. 32, no. 1, pp 80 - 90, 2017.